

Analysis of Impact of Landscaping on Sustainable Environmental Management in Wamakko Local Government Area of Sokoto State, Nigeria

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This study examines the impacts of landscaping on sustainable environmental management in Wamakko Local Government Area of Sokoto State, Nigeria. The research aimed to identify the socio-economic characteristics of landscapers, determine the level of landscaping practices, assess its environmental impacts, and examine the constraints faced in adopting landscaping for sustainability. A purposive sampling technique was used to select Wamakko LGA, while random sampling was employed to select 30 respondents from Kalambaina, Arkilla, and Gwiwa. Data were collected through structured questionnaires and analyzed using descriptive statistics and chi-square analysis. Findings revealed that the majority of landscapers were male, within the age range of 31–40 years, married, and possessed higher educational qualifications. Landscaping practices in the study area were predominantly softscape, involving the cultivation of trees, shrubs, and flowers, with most respondents engaging in it as a source of income and employment. The study further showed that landscaping contributes significantly to environmental sustainability through temperature regulation, environmental beautification, psychological well-being, and vegetation conservation. However, several constraints hinder effective landscaping practices, including inadequate funding, lack of skilled personnel, poor maintenance practices, climatic challenges, land tenure issues, and high cost of maintenance. The chi-square test indicated a significant relationship between landscaping and sustainable environmental management, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. The study concludes that landscaping plays a vital role in promoting sustainable environmental management in the study area. It recommends increased government support through funding, training, provision of improved plant varieties, and awareness creation to enhance landscaping practices and sustainability outcomes.

Key Word: Analysis, Impact, Landscaping, Sustainable, Environmental Management, Wamakko.

INTRODUCTION

For a country or a region to become environmentally sustainable, it means that all the parameters that confer environmental sustainability must have been adequately taken care of. There will also be less poverty among its citizens, food security, less conflict, use of clean technology in the industrial sector etc. In general, the

environment provides all life support systems in the air, on water and on land as well as the materials for fulfilling all developmental aspirations.

Like any developing nation, Nigeria faces some challenges in its developmental stride and efforts to improve the quality of life of its citizens. However, to promote environmental sustainability, the National Environment Policy of 1999 is a key policy document that stipulates the principles for sustainable development. Policies and programmes under broad categories of the

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environmental pillar are related to forestry, biodiversity, pollution control, land degradation, water management, climate change, marine and coastal environment, clean energy, and environmental crime. Government has taken the issues of environmental pollution and degradation seriously.

Various national efforts have been put in place at all levels of governance to promote environmental sustainability in the context of national sustainable development. To complement the effort of the Federal Ministry of Environment, agencies such as National Oil Spill Detection and Response Agency (NOSDRA) and National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA), were created respectively in 2006 and 2007. NOSDRA has the mandate to implement the national oil spill contingency plan. NESREA has responsibility to enforce all environmental laws, guidelines, policies, standards and regulations in Nigeria, as well as enforce compliance with the provisions of all international agreements, protocols, conventions and treaties on the environment to which Nigeria is a signatory (FGN Report, 2012). Considering most attempts for sustainable environmental management, horticultural landscaping has been considered as well as a major means of sustainable environmental management Sustainability goes beyond being a purely environmental issue and includes economic viability as well as social acceptability (Okeagu *et al.*, 2016).

Landscapes and the environment constitute primary territorial and functional settings for a multifunctional farm. Since the last decade, the ecological diversity, biocultural heterogeneity, and aesthetic quality of the rural landscape have overcome a conservative productive model of agricultural monoblocks with specialized production. The application of landscape ecology to food system research has brought benefits for both disciplines, and the integrative analysis of food systems poses new challenges in scientific branches dealing with sustainability (Abbas, 2008). Multifunctional farming improves ecological stability and biodiversity, provides many ecosystem services, delivering benefits for a wide spectrum of the human population, and prevents natural hazards; some farms are important producers of renewable energy. Nassauer and Opdam (2016), defined landscape design as “any intentional change of landscape pattern for the purpose of sustainably providing ecosystem services while recognizably meeting societal needs”. Target farms’ production and society demands should coincide with landscape and environmental potentials (Ejumudo and Nwador, 2014). Deep respect and understanding of the natural environment are mirrored in permaculture farms and farms practicing ecodesign, and both kinds of farms often transform their knowledge into educational courses organized by the farms (Binali, 2014).). Therefore this research work is aimed at studying the impacts of

landscaping on sustainable environmental management using Sokoto metropolis as a case study.

Most residents of Nigeria, Sokoto state to be precise use the environment in three basic ways. One, as a resource bank succeeding that the environment supplies them with raw materials needed to maintain their existence as well as their social and technological structures. Two, as a habitat people require more space per individual than any other species and three, and thirdly as sink for wastes human beings produce more waste than other species. As people migrate to towns and development expands, these three important uses of the environment manifest in various dimensions both positively and negatively. The most common challenges of engagement of landscaping in environmental sustainability in the study is that more farmers are into cropping and livestock while lesser farmers are into horticulture and landscaping this might be as a result that most residents do not see or have little knowledge on the impact of landscaping to their environmental sustainability. When urban centers grow without proper planning, it causes growth of slums. Therefore this study is aimed at studying the impacts of landscaping on sustainable environmental management in Sokoto metropolis.

The research questions are

1. What are the Socio-economic characteristics of landscapers in the study area?
2. What is the level of landscaping practice in the study area?
3. What are the impacts of landscaping on environmental sustainability in the study area?
4. What are the constraints faced in landscapers towards environmental sustainability in the study area?

The broad objective of this research work is to know the specific the impacts of landscaping on sustainable environmental management in the study area. As well as aimed:

1. To identify the socio economic characteristics of the landscapers in the study area.
2. To determine the level of landscaping practice in the study area.
3. To examine the impacts of landscaping on sustainable environment in the study area.
4. To investigate the constraints faced in landscaping towards environmental sustainability in the study area.

The Research Hypotheses is

H₀: There is no significant relationship between landscaping and sustainable environmental management.

This study would provide the research organizations and empirical reports for further and modification of the

(Map of Sokoto State Showing Major Areas of Sokoto, Notable settlements, District headquarters, Wamakko LGA, and other districts)

package to meet the expectations of ultimate beneficiaries. By large the findings from this research will provide a framework for policy makers and extension workers to formulate or review policies and strategies that are improved and residents and farmers involvement in landscaping as a practice to for sustainable environmental management in the study area.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The Study Area

This research work is aimed at studying the impact of landscaping on sustainable environmental management a case study of Wamakko local government Area of Sokoto. Wamakko Local Government Area Sokoto is a Local Government Area in Sokoto State, Nigeria. Its headquarters is in the town of Wamakko (or Wamakko) on the Sokoto River. It has an area of 697 km² and a population of 179,619 at the 2006 census. The district's yearly temperature is 32.98°C (91.36°F) and it is 3.52% higher than Nigeria's averages. Wamakko typically receives about 35.8 millimeters (1.41 inches) of precipitation and has 49.12 rainy days (13.46% of the time) annually. To show variation within the months and not just the monthly totals, we show the rainfall

accumulated over a sliding 31-day period centered on each day of the year. Wamakko experiences extreme seasonal variation in monthly rainfall. The rainy period of the year lasts for 5.1 months, from May 6 to October 10, with a sliding 31-day rainfall of at least 0.5 inches. The month with the most rain in Wamakko is August, with an average rainfall of 6.4 inches. The rainless period of the year lasts for 6.9 months, from October 10 to May 6. The month with the least rain in Wamakko is December, with an average rainfall of -0.0 inches (Weather Spark, 2022). The concentration of wealth, prestige, the political power and religious learning centers in Wamakko attracted large numbers of rural-urban migrants, both from the neighboring state and from distance regions. Presently the notable areas in Wamakko Local Government includes, Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic, State College of Legal and Islamic Studies, State University, National Youth Services Corps camp (NYSC), Amusement Park etc. As of 2022 random population census, the research conducted by National Bureau of Statistics, the estimated rural – urban migrants in the area is about 4,536 and it's increasing at the rate of 10% annually (National Bureau of Statistics, Nigeria, 2022). Wamakko Local government is mainly populated by Hausa people. It also comprises four villages: *Kammata*, *Gwamatse*, *Kauran Kimaba* and *Kokani Cidawa*. The inhabitants are mostly farmers and livestock herders but this research is aimed at studying

Table 4.1 Distribution of Landscapers according to their age.

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
15 – 20 years	0	0
21 – 30 years	9	30
31 – 40 years	11	36.7
41 – 50 years	9	30
51 and above	1	3.3
Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

Table 4.2: Distribution of Landscapers According to their Gender.

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	30	100
Female	0	0
Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

the impact of landscaping on sustainable environmental management in Wamakko Local government area of Sokoto.

Sampling Procedure and Sample Size

Wamakko Local government area was purposively selected and random sampling was used to selected 30 landscapers and households within the study area, due to large size of the target population, 10 respondents each were randomly selected in which data was collected from the following areas which includes; Kalambaina, Arkilla, and Gwiwa respectively. Due to large size of the target population and low participation in landscaping within entire Wamakko LGA from the preliminary research of this research, this design was the appropriate design to identify the problems of this research and to conform accuracy to data needed.

Instrument for the data collection

A well designed, comprehensive and well-structured questionnaire was administered through interview schedule with the landscapers in the districts of Wamakko local government consisting *districts of* Kalambaina, Arkilla and Gwiwa with the involvements of occupants of landscaped buildings, offices and buildings in the areas were selected within the local government area in acquiring their knowledge and experiences on the impact of landscaping on sustainable environmental management in the area and their level of practices of landscaping.

Method of Data Analysis

Objective i, ii and iii was analyzed using descriptive

statistic of frequency and percentage while objective iv will be achieved using Chi square to test the hypothesis of the study by examining the impact of landscaping on sustainable environmental management.

$$X^2 = \frac{(O - E)^2}{E}$$

Where,

X = Chi square value

O = Observed value

E = Expected value

RESULTS

SECTION A: Socioeconomic Characteristics of the Landscapers

Table 4.1 below shows that nom of the landscapers are age range between 15 – 20 years old, 9 landscapers representing (30%) are between 21 – 30years old, 11 landscapers representing (36.7%) are between 31 – 40years old, while 9 landscapers representing (30%) shows the landscapers that are 41 – 50years and only 1 landscaper was recorded to be above 51years old and above. The highest age range of landscapers in the study area is between 31 – 40 years old which implies that older people are into landscaping in the study area. This can be compared to their strength and capabilities of working.

This table 4.2 below shows that 30 of the respondents are male, implies that 100% of the landscapers are male, this can be traced or contrast to the fact that most men are into landscaping in the study area whereby women

Table 4.3 Distribution of landscapers according to their Religion.

Religion	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Islamic	27	90
Christianity	3	10
Traditional	0	0
Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

Table 4.4 Distribution of landscapers according to their Highest Academic qualifications

Academic Qualifications	Frequency	Percentage (%)
No formal Education	0	0
Quranic School	0	0
Primary School Leaving Certificate	0	0
Secondary School Leaving Certificate	0	0
Higher Institutions	30	100
Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

Table 4.5 Distribution of landscapers according to their Marital Status.

Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Single	6	20
Married	24	80
Widowed	0	0
Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

are into others business activities, determining the concept of this study, 100% of the respondents are male Table 4.3 below shows that 27 landscapers representing (90%) of the study are Muslims while only 3 landscapers in the study area are Christians this is traced to the fact that the study area is dominated by most Muslims and no Christians or other religion are into farming activities or residents of the study area.

Table 4.4 below shows that all the landscapers in the study area had higher institutional education representing 100% landscapers representing. This implies that all the landscapers in the study area had acquired certificate of higher institutions. This can be attributed to the fact that majority of the respondent are young and are trained in the field of landscaping before engaging in the landscaping as a business and environmental sustainability through landscaping.

Table 4.5 below shows that 6 (20%) of the landscapers are single while 24 (80%) of the landscapers are married. This implies that most of the respondents are married.

Table 4.6 below shows respondents according to their family size, 13(43.3%) of the landscapers are between 1 – 5 in family size, while 17 (56.7%) of the landscapers are between 6 – 10 numbered in family size. This implies that most of the respondents are married and are

having more dependents family size.

SECTION B: Determine the Level of Landscaping practice in the Study Area.

Table 4.7 below shows the kind of landscaping the landscapers in the study area, 100% of the landscapers in the study area are into the landscaping practice and they grows either perennial flowers, shrubs, succulents and trees. This implies that all the landscapers in the study area are really into landscaping practice as either for environmental sustainability or as a business venture. Table 4.8 below shows what motivates the landscapers in the study area to engage in landscaping practices, 9 (30%) of the landscapers are into landscaping majorly for beautification of their environments and surrounding, while 19(63.3%) of the landscapers in the study area are majorly into landscaping as a business and job opportunity. This implies that majority of the landscapers in the study area are into landscaping practice as a means of business opportunity, whereas 2(6.7%) of the landscapers in the study area are into landscaping for environmental modification purposes which may be relate to (temperature control, and weather and climatic control modification of the environment for sustainable

Table 4.6 Distribution of landscapers according to their Family Size.

Family Size	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1 – 5	13	43.3
6 – 10	17	56.7
11 – 15	0	0
Above 15	0	0
Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

Table 4.7 Distribution of landscapers on the kind of landscaping they engage in the Study Area.

Landscaping	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Hardscape (Non Living Elements; (concrete, bricks and stones))	0	0
Softscape (Growing perennial flowers, shrubs, succulents and trees)	30	100
Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.8 Distribution of landscapers on what motivates them to engage in landscaping in the study area.

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Beautification Purposes	9	30%
Aesthetic Purpose	0	0
Business and Job Opportunity	19	63.3
Environmental Modification purposes	2	6.7
Others	0	0
Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

Table 4.9 Distribution of landscapers according to the environmental implementations of landscaping practice in the study area.

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Trees and Floriculture plantation	20	66.7
Landscaping for soil erosion	0	0
Provision of Landscape features for tourism	7	23.3
Landscaping for Scientific Research	3	10
Others	0	0
Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

environment).

Table 4.9 below shows the environmental implementations of landscaping practice that the landscapers in the study area are into in the study area, 20(66.7%) of the landscapers in the study area plants trees and floriculture, while 7(23.3%) of the landscapers provides landscape features for tourism such as: Greenery Garden for show, turf grass for sporting, fencing and beautified environments for social events, providing that high quality landscapes can strengthen local economies by attracting residents and investment to

an area, as well as tourists. Rural landscapes support a range of primary production activities such as farming, forestry and horticulture. While 3(10%) of the landscapers in the study area are into landscaping for scientific research.

Table 4.10 shows the economic benefits that the landscapers in the study area derives from landscaping practices, 14(46.7%) of the respondents in the study area involves in landscaping as a major means of employment creation while 3(10%) of the landscapers in the study area are deriving economic benefits of landscaping

Table 4.10 Distribution of landscapers from the economic benefits they derive from landscaping practice in the study area.

Economic Benefit	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Employment Creation	14	46.7
Landscaping features for social activities	3	10
Lawn and Grasses for cooler environment	9	30
Contracted Services	3	10
Exporting Services	1	3.3
Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

Table 4.11 Distribution of landscapers on the health impacts of landscaping on sustainable environment in the study area.

Health Impacts	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Disease Control	6	20
Temperature Modification	13	43.3
Psychological Health Control	5	16.7
Environmental Beautification	6	20
Others	0	0
Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

through creating landscaping features for social activities, as well as 9(30%) of the landscapers in the study area generates their economy from landscaping by creating lawn and grasses for cooler environment as a business, also 3(10%) of the landscapers in the study area are into landscaping as major economic benefits by contracted services while 1(3.3%) of the landscapers are into exporting services of landscaping materials.

SECTION C: To Examine the Impacts of Landscaping on Sustainable Environment in the Study Area.

Table 4.11 below shows the landscapers responses in regard to the health impacts of landscaping on sustainable environment in the study area. 6(20%) of the landscapers in the study area engages in landscaping in response to disease control which can be related to the plantation of resistant varieties in controlling diseases by buying resistant varieties when they are available, also 13(43.3%) of the landscapers in the study area are into landscaping for temperature modification of the area which involves engaging sustainable landscape design approach as mitigating strategies to modify the temperature. Also 5(16.7%) of the landscapers in the study area engages in landscaping for psychological health control by providing serene environment for relaxation and ease from depression and stress. While 6(20%) of the landscapers in the study area are into landscaping for environmental beautification which shows the beauty of the environment and in provision of the aesthetic values of the environmental properties. Table 4.12 below shows the environmental impacts of landscaping on sustainable environment,

16(53.3%) of the landscapers in the study area engages in landscape majorly as a means of livelihood, while 2(6.7%) of the landscapers in the study area engages in landscape in their area for soil erosion and 12(40%) of the landscapers in the study area are into landscaping in their environment for conservable vegetation such as; involving in surrounding landscape that influences functional diversity of plant species in the area and as well conservation planning attempts to address conservation problems by drawing on knowledge of natural ecosystems and solutions and preservation against environmental disasters such as wild fires, erosion, floods, earthquakes, and droughts. Although the causes of these natural environmental disasters do not involve human activities, but in some cases the effects are worsened by the influence of people.

Table 4.13 below shows the economic importance of landscaping in the study area, 9(30%) of the landscapers in the study area generates their economic benefits from the boosting of occupancy rate of landscaped housing, while 11(36.7%) of the landscapers in the study area responded to the fact that landscaping helps in increasing property value which implies that A well-landscaped home has a significant price advantage over a home with no landscaping. While 9(30%) of the landscapers responded that landscaping majorly is for creation of job opportunities and had contributed greatly to acquiring employment in the study area, and 1(3.3%) of the landscapers believes that landscaping greatly contribute through operation and maintenance income generation, this is due to the fact that landscaping business amounts fall under the internal revenue service, and so, all these landscaping services are tax-deductible which means it

Table 4.12 Distribution of environmental impacts of landscaping on sustainable environment in the study area.

Environmental Impacts	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Means of Livelihood	16	53.3
Control of Soil Erosion	2	6.7
Creation of Passage for water run offs	0	0
Pests Control	0	0
Provision of Conservable Vegetation	12	40
Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

Table 4.13 Distribution of landscapers in response to the economic landscaping in the study area.

Economic Importance	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Boost Occupancy Rate	9	30
Increase rent Value	0	0
Increase Property Value	11	36.7
Creation of Job Opportunities	9	30
Operation and Maintenance Income	1	3.3
Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

Table 4.14 Distribution of landscapers showing agreement that a well landscaping is very essential for sustainable environmental management.

Level of Agreement	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes (Agreed)	28	93.3
No (Do not Agreed)	2	6.7
Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

Table 4.15 Distribution of landscapers in response how a well-designed landscaping sustains environmental management in the study area.

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Temperature Modification	6	20
Foster Confidence and Satisfying Environment	15	50
Provides mental health benefits	6	20
Helps in building protection	2	6.7
Prioritizing water drainage solutions	1	3.3
Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

contributes also to the government and to the landscapers.

Table 4.14 below shows the level of agreement of landscapers asking them if a well designed landscaping is very essential for sustainable environmental management, 28(93.3%) agreed yes while only 2(6.7%) of the landscapers agreed no in response to the sustainability of landscaping for environmental management. Table 4.15 below shows the responses of landscapers in the study area on how a well-designed

landscape sustain environmental management, 6(20%) responded that landscaping sustains with temperature modification while, 15(50%) responded that landscaping sustains through as it foster confidence and satisfying environment through reduction the stress and tension which affect the well-being of the inhabitants of the study area and as well landscape design and features are important because they contribute significantly to our well-being and quality of life. 6(20%) of the landscapers supported that landscaping provides mental health

Table 4.16 Distribution of landscapers in response to the managerial constraints faced by landscapers towards environmental sustainability in the study area.

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Architectural Planning and Designing	4	13.3
Unimproved Routine Maintenance Schedule	7	23.3
Needed Funds or Capital at time due	5	16.7
Unprofessional Personnel's	14	46.7
Others	0	0
Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

Table 4.17 Distribution of landscapers in response to the physical factors creating problems for landscapers in environmental sustainability in the study area.

Physical Factors	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Site Designing and Functionality	3	10
Functional and Healthy Landscape	7	23.3
Climatic Condition	20	66.7
Land Topography (Slopes, Hills etc.)	0	0
Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

Table 4.18 Distribution of landscapers in response to the other constraints creating problems for landscapers in environmental sustainability in the study area.

Constraints	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Pests and Diseases	3	10
High Cost of Maintenance	7	23.3
Land Tenure Security	10	33.3
Unavailability of Improved varieties	10	33.3
Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

benefits through reduction in anxiety and also seeing the colors around you, smell the fresh air, listen to the birds, touch the plants, and taste what the garden has to offer. Surprisingly, can help to improve mood and as well, 2(6.7%) of the landscapers believes that landscaping helps in building protection by prioritizing water drainage solutions, landscapers protect natural waterways, create rain gardens and sustainable area in the study area as supported by 1(3.3%) of the landscapers.

SECTION D: To identify the constraints faced by landscapers towards environmental sustainability in the study area.

Table 4.16 below shows the managerial constraints faced by the landscapers in the study area towards environmental sustainability, 4(13.3%) of the landscapers supported the architectural planning and designing, 7(23.3%) supported that unimproved routine maintenance schedule is a constraint, 5(16.7%) of the

landscapers reported that needed funds and capital at time due is a major constraint while 14(46.7%) of the landscapers supported that unprofessional personnel and skilled workers for landscaping practices is a constraint in the study area. Managing a landscape means guiding future change and development in other to foster growth of the landscape element. It requires the landscape manager to be ready to adapt to everything mother-nature throws its way. Many landscape managers stick to a rigid maintenance schedule and some deliberately led plants to overgrow resulting to total clearance of such plants. This positive problem affects the life of plants negatively as against the normative routine maintenance which helps avoid cost of replacement whenever possible.

Table 4.17 below shows the physical factors creating problems for landscapers in environmental sustainability in the study area. 3(10%) of the landscapers reported that site designing and functionality has been a problem for landscapers in the study area, as well as 7(23.3%) of

Figure 4.1 Showing significant relationship between landscaping and sustainable environmental management X= Landscaping, Y=Sustainable Environmental Management

Table 4.19 Showing the significant relationship between Landscaping and sustainable environmental management in the study area.

O	E	O-E	(O-E) ²	X ² (O-E) ² /E
4	15	-11	121	8.1
7	15	-8	64	4.3
5	15	-10	100	6.7
14	15	-1	1	0.1
30	60	-30	286	19.2

Variables	Hypothesis Negative -
Beautification Purpose	8.1
Aesthetic Purpose	4.3
Business and Job Opportunity	6.7
Environmental Modification Purposes	0.1

Using =
$$X^2 = \frac{(O-E)^2}{E}$$

Where,

X = Chi square value

O = Observed value

E = Expected value

Expected Return (E) = 286/30 = 9.53.

the landscapers reported that functional and healthy landscape has been a major problem in the study area that landscapers are facing, 20(66.7%) of the landscapers reported that climatic condition is of a major problem facing landscaping practice in the study area.

Table 4.18 below shows the response of landscapers in response to the other constraints creating problems for

landscapers in environmental sustainability in the study area. Other constraints faced by the landscapers towards environmental sustainability in the study area includes; pests and diseases through animal encroachments either by rodents, as well as high cost of maintenance of landscaping management both in the plantation and the effectiveness of the landscaping practices, land tenure

and security is another major problem facing landscapers in the study area. Unavailability of improved varieties is of major problem affecting the effectiveness of landscaping practice in the study area.

Possible solutions towards the constraints faced by the landscapers towards environmental sustainability in the study area.

In response by the reports from the landscapers agreed that government can help the landscapers on association formation to improve their interests in landscaping in the study area, as well as government can help in loan and grants provision, access to improved varieties and mechanization can be a major support from the governments on how they can support the landscapers to improve their interests in landscaping practices and that government could help in training and lecture to the landscapers on how the landscaping can be improved and to provide trained personnel among them to others. As landscaping is a taxable operation within the nation and add to the Gross Domestic Profit of the nation at large.

Testing of Hypothesis

In the process of conducting this research project, I developed a hypothesis in chapter one, thus there is significant relationship between landscaping and sustainable environmental management.

H₀: There is no significant relationship between landscaping and sustainable environmental management in the study area.

The calculated value was 19.2 while the expected value was 9.53. Thus Chi Square Method states that if the calculated chi-square value is more than the value of chi-square in the table at 10% level of significance the null hypothesis will be rejected. Therefore, this result shows that there is significance difference between landscaping and sustainable environmental management in the study area.

CONCLUSION

Landscaping for its sustainability values cannot be underestimated as it is designed to be both attractive and in balance with the local climate and environment and it should require minimal resource inputs. Thus, the design must be "functional, cost-efficient, visually pleasing, environmentally friendly and maintainable". Landscaping as part of sustainable development, it pays close attention to preserving limited resources, reducing waste, and preventing air, water and soil pollution. Compost, fertilization, integrated pest management, using the right plant in the right place, appropriate use of turf and

xeriscaping (water-wise gardening) are all components of sustainable landscaping. Therefore, landscaping practices is very essential as it helps for sustainable environmental management.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this research, the following recommendations were made:

1. Landscapers should be careful to select the best and appropriate varieties of landscaping materials in its adaptation states to climatic conditions of their environments.
2. To improve landscaping activities in Wamakko Local Government Area of Sokoto, governments, research institutions and private foundations should support the development of landscaping practice in Wamakko Local Government Area of Sokoto State to enable the promotion of landscaping practice in most rural areas of Wamakko LGA, Sokoto.
3. Improved Landscaping techniques are critical factors in developing science and technology policy and business strategy for better landscaping on sustainable environmental management. As with many other emerging techniques, should be encourage continuing among landscapers as these will enhance the reliability of landscapes upon which business, government and academic leaders can base science and technology decisions.
4. Training of landscapers should be encouraged and awareness creations should be valued to get more landscapers into landscaping practice in Wamakko Local Government Area, Sokoto.

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